

Prioritizing Association-Rules for Product Recommendation: A Case Study In E-Retailing

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Abstract

E-commerce web sites enable businesses to utilize recommendations that help to increase cross-sales by providing relevant products. The traditional Market Basket Analysis relies on finding products often purchased together in prior basket data. In such cases, selecting the most appropriate offer requires evaluation of association rules through various strategies for rule selection. With an emphasis on the recency of transactions, this study presents a slight modification in the Apriori algorithm, which is widely used in association rule discovery. Weighted rule mining techniques help to prioritize transactions regarding attributes, including the recency, customer, or purchase total. Our study demonstrates a case study where the itemset support calculation with a weighted approach favors more recent transactions. The findings indicate notable decreases in completion time, while prioritizing more recent transactions with the aim to obtain time-sensitive and potentially more useful recommendations.

Keywords: *Weighted Association Rule Mining, Frequent Itemset Mining, Market Basket Analysis*

1 Introduction

Association Rule Mining is among the unsupervised learning techniques in data mining [1] that analyze transactional data and extracts useful patterns about how items come together. The technique has been applied in various problems, where its name is used along with terms 'Affinity Analysis', or 'Market Basket Analysis' regarding the problem domain.

The Apriori algorithm by Agrawal et al. [2] has been introduced with an emphasis on its ability to scale on large datasets and the ease of use for intuitive outputs. For more than two decades, the conventional algorithm for itemset discovery has received intense attention. However, the algorithm discards the count of items, and such exclusion was noted as a limitation for the use of extracted information on some domains where numeric attributes in rules might signify important conclusions. In this manner, the reduction of item co-occurrences into a binary relation was underlined as a constraint by various researchers.

The Apriori algorithm has been extended by various studies to adapt to different constraints or assumptions. Among such modifications, some methods propose adding weights that prioritize items, transactions, or even both. These kinds of studies often examine transaction and item

relationships using numerical variables and are often described as weighted rule mining techniques. This study attempts to present a case study by utilizing a slightly modified version of the algorithm to discover frequent purchase patterns by analyzing recency-based weighted transactions. For this purpose, monthly orders were prioritized based on their recency. In this manner, our study handles basket data as a temporal dataset where purchase date corresponds to the temporal attribute.

Our approach was tested on a dataset obtained from an e-retailer (adepo.com), which had been one of the leading online groceries in İzmir, Turkey. The basket data analyzed consists of 3163 purchase records in 340 categories, ordered in November 2013. Recency-based weighting was held by applying a modification on the calculation of item/itemset support on the first phase of the original Apriori algorithm. For this purpose, the source code was edited in the RuleGenerator software, which consists of an Apriori implementation along with a graphical user interface. The software was previously introduced in [3] to discover brand-wise and category-wise association rules. A series of tests were held in which slightly different coefficients have been used to adjust the effect of recency.

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Our findings present a comparison of the total counts of itemsets and rules obtained. Our results suggest that analyzing basket data by assigning recency-based transaction weights might considerably shorten completion time while reducing the count of rules in our test data.

2 Association Rule Mining

In data mining, association rule mining techniques discover patterns that frequently occur together in data. Among the rule mining algorithms, the Apriori algorithm [2] efficiently discovers frequent itemsets, and generates association rules of the form $X \rightarrow Y$, which represent co-occurrence of items in datasets.

The technique involves two phases, including frequent itemset mining and rule generation [4:98]. The first phase relies on finding the count of occurrences for items, filtering items that occur below a threshold, and generating itemsets iteratively. Subsequently, itemsets are decomposed into consequent and antecedents to populate rules; and those rules that satisfy a confidence threshold are assumed potentially interesting. The rules are then evaluated by several measures [5] and explored for problem-specific purposes.

As noted in the first phase, the items are directly counted in conventional frequent pattern mining. The underlying idea in counting was attributed to the assumption of equal importance in transactions [6].

2.1 Weighted Rule Mining

Many practices of association rule mining necessitate assigning different weights on items or transactions. As an example, association rule mining is often used for market basket analysis, where the significance of customers differs. Accordingly, such differences might be brought into attention by weighting transactions [7]. More generally, such practice in market basket analysis is occasionally expressed with the "utility mining" notion, which corresponds to mining rules regarding both item prices and counts purchased [8].

In one of the earlier studies, Ramkumar et al. [9] discussed several approaches in weighted rule mining. The authors suggested that counting the transactions, which include the item(s), is sufficient for the calculation of the support measure in an unweighted configuration. By this means, weighting

transactions is usually simpler than weighting items [9].

Another motive to weight transactions depends on the effect of time. Weighted frequent-itemset mining algorithms can find time-sensitive results if transactions are weighted appropriately [10]. Gan et al. [11] noted that taking the recency of data is crucial to properly measure the interestingness of patterns in databases where observations in data are sensitive to time. Moreover, the authors explained such necessity by mentioning the market basket data and noted that the recency of transactions should be considered to extract up-to-date patterns rather than out-of-date results. As a further notice on market basket analysis, Lin et al. [12] noticed the importance of recency from a decision-makers' perspective and noted that rules occasionally demonstrate shopping patterns that vary over time, and identification of such patterns in more recent data is crucial for decision-makers. With such justification, both studies [11] [12] have proposed customized techniques that take recency of transactions into account during frequent itemset mining.

Weighting transactions is still relevant considering the effect of prices on purchase decisions. Regarding the prices set for the products, prior purchase records might be described as nonstationary time series because of the typical increases in the price level due to inflation [4:465]. From this perspective, it might be argued that the importance of out-of-date transactions should be reduced in market basket analysis due to the increasing probability of price changes over time. In addition to the previous reasons, Ramkumar et al. [9] noted that contextual factors such as the profit or the significance of the customer might justify the application of association rule mining with transaction weights.

Item-based weighting is another approach in weighted association rule mining. Sun and Bai [6] introduced an alternative rule mining technique where items are weighted according to the link structure across transactions and items. The motive in that approach was described as items of high importance are included in many transactions, and transactions with high importance involve items with high importance. Furthermore, Vo et al. [13] proposed alternative methods for frequent weighted itemset mining, where items have weights, and transactions are weighted as the

average weight of items included. Another study that develops an extended rule mining technique with weighted items was proposed by Wang et al. [14]. The weighting approach was described using a market basket analysis scenario, where purchased volumes correspond to weights. Moreover, the study also explores the range of volumes and includes a novel “density” measure to select the appropriate interval that results in higher confidence scores achieved in the extracted rules.

Sun [15] proposed a modification of the classical Apriori algorithm by implementing weights for items and transactions, which results in accomplishing improved execution time while reducing memory requirements in comparison with the original algorithm. Specifically, the idea in the proposed method was replacing the binary relations among transactions and items with a weight matrix. The calculation of weights incorporates a strategy which slightly increases the supports calculated for rare items and works the other way for frequent items. The authors argued this capability due to its potential use in extracting valuable but rare findings.

3 Methodology

As in many weighted rule mining techniques, our study involves assigning weights into transactions. As noted in the prior section, the inclusion of recency is possible by assigning weights into transactions. In this way, more recent transactions are given higher importance, while the importance of older transactions degrades in proportion to the recency factor.

In contrast with several approaches in weighted rule mining, our solution includes minimal modification in the original Apriori algorithm. The only change was made within the procedure for the calculation of support for items and item-sets. Rather than counting the total count of transactions that involve an item or itemset, our update relies on simply adding the weights of such transactions. However, this step relies on adjusting appropriate weights for transactions beforehand.

The process needs to be detailed for the basket data in our case study. A recency-based transaction weighting of basket data results in higher prioritizing of more recent purchase decisions. Moreover, older purchase records that might still

have relevance are accounted for, despite their weaker priority.

Each transaction was assigned weights to apply the recency effect on transactional data. In fact, weights solely depend on the date, and the weight for the present date is initialized as 1 in the first step. Next, prior periods are weighted with a recursive approach by multiplication with a periodic rate. By this means, our approach is analogous to net present value calculation in finance, where the interest rate is used to adjust cash flows occurring at different times. Accordingly, it was assumed that prior transactions lose their significance by a rate each period; thus, a coefficient, namely ‘rate of diminishment’ is defined.

Using the rate of diminishment, the weights for transactions are calculated as in the following:

$$\text{Let } r: \text{Rate of diminishment} \quad \text{where } 0 < r < 1 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Let } T_i: i^{\text{th}} \text{ transaction} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Let } R: \text{A scalar function where:} \quad (3)$$

$$R(T_i) = \text{Total days after } T_i \quad (4)$$

Accordingly,

$$w(T_i) = (1 - r)^{R(T_i)} \quad (5)$$

Unsurprisingly, setting $r=0$ would result in identical support scores with the Apriori algorithm. The difference was in support calculation that takes summarization of transaction weights, instead of transaction counts.

Letting r as the rate of diminishment and assuming t for today, the weights for transactions will be calculated as in the following:

Table 1. Comparison of Iterations

Day	Weights for transactions
t	1
t-1	(1-r)
t-2	(1-r) ²
t-3	(1-r) ³
t-4	(1-r) ⁴
t-5	(1-r) ⁵

A major benefit of weighted rule mining was reported in previous studies was the significant reduction in the count of association rules and frequent patterns. This is promising in order to examine purchase behaviors by reducing uninteresting rules. Moreover, weighted rule

mining is reported to improve performance in terms of the time required for analysis. For such reason, the application of the weighted rule mining technique might help to try analyses using lower support thresholds on the same duration.

4 Findings

Our dataset involves the same dataset in [3] obtained from an e-retailer. The basket data consists of monthly purchase transactions recorded in November 2013. Therefore, it should be noted that a dataset captured in a more extended period would have been more useful for recency-based transaction weighting, and the one-month period of purchases is a major limitation for our study.

This section presents several tests that have been conducted where the recency effect is increased by incrementing the rate of diminishment. In each test, rule extraction from the basket data was held using the parameters below:

- Support: 2%
- Confidence: 25%

The durations, count of itemsets, and rules extracted with our approach incorporate differences from the original Apriori algorithm. After each execution, the count of itemsets and rules were noted. Accordingly, a comparison of the results obtained in consecutive tests was presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of Iterations

Rate of Diminishment (%)	Itemset Count	Rule Count	Duration (Sec)
0	919	1070	115.64
1	651	708	78.82
2	503	534	47.09
3	371	407	37.30
4	268	291	22.81
5	206	204	17.62
6	167	160	14.55
7	126	112	10.55
8	101	89	9.44
9	86	64	8.70
10	72	55	8.15

The findings in Table 2 demonstrate a decrease in itemset and rule counts. The underlying factor in this decrease might be attributed to the reduced weights of less recent transactions. In this way, old

purchase records will be given less importance over time.

Another noticeable finding is the gradual decrease in completion time as the rate increases from 0% to 10%. The 10% reduction in periodic weights might be excessively high, especially for our case where each period corresponds to a day. Nevertheless, the improvement from 0% to 2% still demonstrates a 59.27% improvement in execution time. As a further note, tests for rule mining were conducted using the *RuleGenerator* software on a moderate laptop with an Intel i5 CPU (8265u).

The decrease in the total rules and itemsets was depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Count of rules and itemsets obtained with tests with rates of diminishment in [0, 10].

As demonstrated in the figure, increasing the rate of diminishment leads to a decrease in total rules and itemsets. However, the slope of the curve signals slightly lower rates of decrease in every increase. Moreover, support calculation with leveraging the rate of diminishment also decreases total execution times. Figure 2 demonstrates the completion times in tests where the rate of diminishment was gradually increased from 0% to 10%.

Figure 2. The durations (sec.) obtained in tests

Although the decrease in total completion times looks promising, the rates “duration/rule” and “duration/itemset” suggest the opposite. The graph in Figure 3 does not imply a consistent decline, as in the previous figure. Nevertheless, the total execution times still greatly benefit from weighting transactions by recency.

Figure 3. Durations (sec.) / rule count

In prior research, Wang et al. [14] reported an increase in the rule confidence scores upon the application of weighted rule mining. The study differs with an item-based weighting approach and the density measure that was included to assess itemsets. For this reason, there is no reason to expect an improvement in our approach regarding the interestingness of rules in terms of confidence measure. Even so, the average confidences obtained in our tests are demonstrated in Figure 4. According to our test results, the average confidence scores vary within the range of 43.11%-46.75%.

Figure 4. Averages of rule confidences obtained in tests

5 Conclusion

Weighted frequent itemset mining methods are specialized forms of frequent pattern mining techniques. Such techniques might either differentiate items or transactions relevant, or even both.

Using weighted itemset mining might help to extract useful results in market basket analysis by providing the opportunity to assign weights on data. The weights have been adjusted regarding the volume and price of products or recency of transactions in prior studies. Variations of the Apriori algorithm have been proposed with the inclusion of weights or weight matrices.

Our study follows prior research on weighting transactions to differentiate purchase records by recency. Moreover, our approach depends on using a coefficient, namely the rate of diminishment, which devaluates transactions within the support-calculation procedure. Our case study on monthly basket data demonstrates significantly reduced counts in both rules and item-sets being discovered. Additionally, modification in the algorithm was possible due to the existence of RuleGenerator software, which had been introduced by the author in prior studies.

As demonstrated in our case study, recency-based weighting in rule mining offers several benefits. The most significant one is the decrease in overall duration for analysis. Our study attempts to demonstrate the benefits with a minor revision in the support-calculation step of the original algorithm. Moreover, the same principle might be applied to the FP-Growth algorithm, which also incorporates a support-calculation step similar to the Apriori algorithm. Furthermore, it might be argued that the proposed approach might facilitate market basket analysis by allowing quicker tests on datasets that span purchase records in more extensive periods.

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